

PREVALENCE OF DEPRESSION AMONG THE CAREGIVERS OF SUBSTANCE USE DISORDER PATIENTS

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Abstract

Objective: To determine the prevalence of depression among the caregivers of substance use disorder patients

Methods: This is a descriptive case study conducted in the Department of Psychiatry and Behavioral Sciences, Jinnah Postgraduate Medical Center (JPMC), Karachi, through a convenience sampling technique from 27th December, 2024 to 26th April 2025. All adult caregivers who are involved in taking care of patients with substance use (any type) disorder of either gender, irrespective of their age, and those who consent to participate were included. HAM-D criteria applied to diagnose and scale the level of depression for caregivers.

Results: Out of 110 participants, the overall mean age was 38.28±14.11 years, and among them, most of the participants were males (n = 94, 85.45%). The most common type of substance abuse was the use of ice/crystal (31.81%, n = 35) followed by cannabis (26.36%, n = 29), opioid/heroin (23.63%, n = 26), and alcohol (18.18%, n = 20). The history of psychiatric illness among caregivers of substance abuse disorder patients was 5.45% (n = 06). The overall prevalence of depression among caregivers of substance abuse disorder patients was 16.36% (n = 18). Among them, most of the caregivers had sub-threshold levels of depression (7.27%, n = 8) while severe depression was observed in 1.82% (n = 2) of the health care givers.

Conclusion: The findings underscore the significant mental health burden experienced by these caregivers and highlight the need for targeted interventions and support services to promote their well-being.

Introduction:

Like everywhere else in the world, Pakistan is also struggling with the growing issue of substance abuse. This disorder poses one of the

single largest threats to the public health of the country (1). The problem is known as “a family illness” and it is very complex, both psychologically and socially. Approximately 246

million people, or one out every twenty individuals aged 15 to 64, were estimated to be illicit drug users in 2018 (2). In South Asia, alcohol topped as the most used substance (21.4% prevalence), followed by cannabis (3.0%), and opioids (0.7%). Somewhere between 17 to 26 percent of alcohol consumers qualified for dependency using the International Classification of Diseases (ICDs) 10 criteria (3). With the rise in patients, the problems confronted by caregivers of different patient categories also increase. This results in difficulties, problems, or adverse occurrences in the life of the patient and his or her relatives. Research shows that caregivers of substance-abusing patients carry a significant burden (4). The primary caregivers for patients suffering from the mental illnesses have a high probability of facing mental challenges, familial problems, and an unsatisfactory standard of living. The caretakers of alcoholic and heroin addict patients carry a moderately severe to a very high burden of caregiving (5). Some studies suggest that the primary caregivers suffering from substance abuse and addiction problems mainly (>33.5%) belong to low-income families residing in rural areas (6). The caregivers for alcoholic patients are predominantly females and unemployed, aged between 25 to 40 years (7). Substance abuse requires high dependence on the substance which increases the family burden and also leads to depression in the caregivers. The rationale behind this research is that there have been very few local studies on how drug abusers and substance abusers / dependents are stressing out caregivers. The purpose of the study is to determine how many of the patients with substance use disorders have depression-stricken caregivers. And, to accord significance to the attendants of these patients in attending to the patients. By this measure, interventions early on, like regular checking of caregivers' depression level and current social support, can help prevent or minimize depression in these caregivers. The actual burden of depression among caregivers known will emphasize the issue and help manage it.

Patients and Methods:

This is a descriptive case study conducted in the Department of Psychiatry and Behavioral Sciences, Jinnah Postgraduate Medical Center

(JPMC), Karachi, through a convenience sampling technique from 27th December, 2024 to 26th April 2025. The sample size was calculated in Open EPI using the formula: $[DEFF * Np(1-P)] / [(d2/Z2 1- a/2*(N-1)+p*(1-p)]$ A total of 110 cases will be taken, using expected percentage of caregivers having depression while taking care of substance use abusers (20%) (8) with 95% confidence interval and 7.5% margin of error.

The inclusion criteria for this study were all adult caregivers who were involved in taking care of patients with substance use (any type) disorder of either gender, irrespective of their age, and those who consented to participate. The exclusion criteria for this study were significant physical or surgical illness, patients with intellectual disability, history of any past psychiatric illness among caregivers, and caregivers with medical problems such as diabetes mellitus, hypertension, asthma, COPD, or CLD that may mask depressive symptoms.

Data collection & analysis:

All the caregivers of patients with substance use and meeting the inclusion and exclusion criteria were enrolled for final analysis. Informed and written consent was taken from all caregivers. Data collected from the Department of Psychiatry, Jinnah Postgraduate Medical Center, Karachi, for baseline and clinical characteristics such as age, gender, area of residence, socioeconomic status, and ethnicity. Details of substance (alcohol/heroin/cannabis/cocaine/ice) were recorded. Hamilton Scale for Depression (HAM-D) criteria are applied to diagnose and scale the level of depression for caregivers. Socioeconomic status is categorized as lower (monthly income <30, 000 PKR), middle (monthly income ≥30, 000 - <150, 000 PKR), and upper (monthly income ≥150, 000 PKR). Educational status is primary if completed 5th standard, secondary if completed till 10th standard, and higher if education was above 10th standard.

The UK National Institute for Health & Clinical Excellence has specified the following "levels of depression" based on the 17-item HAM-D. It previously used the terms in parentheses, which are those of the American Psychiatric Association (9)

- Not depressed: 0-7
- Mild (subthreshold): 8-13
- Moderate (mild): 14-18
- Severe (moderate): 19-22
- Very severe (severe): >23

All data collected in a structured questionnaire then entered and analyzed using SPSS V. 21. Categorical data (such as gender, education status, area of residence, marital status, social status, ethnicity, type of substance abuse, past history of psychiatric illness, and scale of depression from not depressed to severe depression) analyzed while mean with standard

deviation calculated for the continuous data like age.

Results:

A total of 110 participants were included for final analysis. The overall mean age was 38.28±14.11 years and among them most of the participants were males (n = 94, 85.45%) while 14.54% (n = 16) were females. Urban dwellers (89.09%, n = 98) were more common than rural (10.9%, n = 12). Most of our study participants were single (60%, n = 66), belongs to middle socio-economic class (70.9%, n = 78), and were of Sindhi ethnic background (52.72%, n = 58). Table 1.

Table 1: Baseline characteristics of study participants (N = 110)

Parameters	Number	Percent
Age - years		
Mean±SD	38.28±14.11	
Gender		
Male	94	85.45
Female	16	14.54
Education status		
Illiterate	12	10.9
Primary	36	32.72
Secondary	28	25.45
Intermediate	18	16.36
≥Graduation	16	14.54
Area of residence		
Urban	98	89.09
Rural	12	10.9
Marital status		
Single	66	60
Married	44	40
Social Class		
Lower	22	20
Middle	78	70.9
Upper	10	9.09
Ethnicity		
Sindhi	58	52.72
Urdu	36	32.72
Punjabi	12	10.9
Balochi	2	1.81
Other	2	1.81

The most common type of substance abuse was the use of ice/crystal (31.81%, n = 35) followed by cannabis (26.36%, n = 29), opioid/heroin (23.63%, n = 26), and alcohol (18.18%, n = 20). Graph 1. In our study we have observed that history of psychiatric illness among care givers of substance abuse disorder patients was 5.45% (n = 06). Graph 2.

Graph 1: Types of substance abuse (N = 110)

Graph 2: History of psychiatric illness among care givers of substance abuse disorder patients (N = 110)

The overall prevalence of depression among care givers of substance abuse disorder patients was 16.36% (n = 18) among them, most of the care givers had sub-threshold level of depression

(7.27%, n = 8) while severe depression was observed in 1.82% (n = 2) of the health care givers. Graph 3.

Graph 3: Scale of depression among care givers of substance abuse disorder patients (N = 110)

Discussion:

Caregivers play a vital role in supporting individuals with substance use disorders (SUDs). Caregivers offer encouragement, understanding, and stability, helping patients navigate the challenges of addiction recovery. Caregivers motivate patients to stay committed to therapy, rehabilitation programs, and medical treatments. Caregiving can be emotionally and physically demanding, so caregivers must prioritize their own well-being to continue providing effective support. Caregivers often face significant stress and emotional challenges, making it essential for them to seek support and resources to maintain their own health while helping (10).

Our study indicates a 16.36% overall prevalence of depression among caregivers of substance use disorder (SUD) patients. This figure highlights that a significant proportion of caregivers are experiencing depressive symptoms. While most of those experiencing depression were at a sub-threshold level (7.27%), the presence of severe depression in 1.82% of the caregivers is also a cause for concern, indicating significant impairment and need for intervention. It's crucial to compare the 16.36% prevalence to the general population. In a study published by Corrigan P estimates that globally, more than 5% of adults suffer from depression (11). While a direct comparison requires accounting for the specific population demographics of the study (age, gender, location etc.), the prevalence in this caregiver group might be elevated compared to

the general population. Caregiving for individuals with SUD is inherently stressful. SUDs often involve unpredictable behaviors, relapse, financial strain, social stigma, and emotional turmoil for the entire family. This chronic stress can significantly contribute to the development of depression in caregivers (12, 13). In our study the presence of severe depression in 1.82% of caregivers warrants immediate attention. Severe depression is associated with significant functional impairment, increased risk of suicidal ideation, and poorer treatment outcomes (14).

In a recently conducted study from Pakistan by the Farasat Ali and colleagues have shown huge number of caregivers suffering from depression (69%) (15). In another study authors have observed that caregivers of drug use disorder patients were shown to have a prevalence of sadness and anxiety of 65% and 46.2%, respectively (16). Akram SM (17) also showed higher prevalence of severe depression (5.2%) among caregivers of substance use disorder as compared to our study's findings. The difference between our study's findings with previously conducted studies could be due to multiple reasons such as higher prevalence in previously conducted studies could be due to over-estimation of symptoms with depression or less skilled / trained caregivers dealing with substance use disorder patients. In our study we also evaluated caregivers with previous history of psychiatric illness and found 5.45% (n = 06) had it. One reason of higher depression among

previously conducted studies could be higher prevalence of history of psychiatric illness among caregivers. That should be evaluated in future studies which is missing in previously conducted studies.

Conclusion:

This study provides valuable insight into the prevalence of depression among caregivers of individuals with SUD. The findings underscore the significant mental health burden experienced by these caregivers and highlight the need for targeted interventions and support services to promote their well-being. Future research should focus on identifying risk factors for depression in this population and developing effective interventions to prevent and treat depressive symptoms. Addressing caregiver mental health is essential for improving the overall well-being of both caregivers and individuals with SUD.

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